

THE USE OF DIFFERENT SHEARING RATE IN DIRECT SHEAR TEST TO DETERMINE DAMPING IN SOILS AND SOIL-CONCRETE INTERFACE FOR INPUT IN PILE DRIVING ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: One of important input in wave propagation in pile driving analysis is the magnitude of damping in large shearing strains or displacement. The uncertainty of this parameters has been elaborated using matching in Pile Driving Analyzer (PDA) of Dynamic Load Test (DLT) where force measured by strain gauges are being matched with the velocity measured by the accelerometers mounted on the piles. However, wave propagation analysis may need to be conducted prior to pile installation, hence the parameters are frequently assumed in wave propagation analysis of pile driving.

This research is laboratory tests using different shearing rates in direct shear tests on soils and soil concrete interface to estimate or calculate damping of soils and soil-concrete or mortar interface as the higher shearing rate will yield higher shear stresses as an influence factor of the damping in soils. The shearing rate applied is 0.01 mm/minutes and 1.0 mm/minutes (100 times faster) to yield the damping effect. The results show that as the rate was increased, the shear stresses also increase. The slow test or quasi static test can be regarded as "static" resulting in static shear stress and the difference in shear stress at high rate can then be used to calculate damping of soils and soil-concrete interface. As a preliminary test, the results are prospective for further development.

Keywords: Direct shear test, damping of soils and soil-pile interface

INTRODUCTION

The effect of damping in soil pile interface is very significant on the behavior of pile during driving. One of important input for wave propagation in pile driving analysis is the magnitude of damping in large shearing strains or displacement. The uncertainty of this parameters have been elaborated using matching in Pile Driving Analyzer (PDA) of Dynamic Load Test (DLT) where force measured by strain gauges are being matched with the velocity measured by the accelerometers mounted on the piles. An important aspect to be understood is that the damping is primarily between soils and pile material interface.

Direct shear test is the most suitable way of simulating the shear resistance between soil and pile material, in particular: concrete. However, the pile driving mechanism causes not only large

displacement between pile and soil, but also in high speed. Hence the purpose of this research is not only to generate soil-pile shear behavior, but also soil-pile damping properties.

Figure 1. Direct Shear Test Simulation for Pile Driving Mechanism

TEST MATERIAL AND TEST PROCEDURES

The tests were conducted for soils and soil concrete interface. For soil-concrete interface the test method is slightly modified where the concrete material is placed below the soil element with slight by lower from the lips of the ring. The test conducted similar to ASTM standard at soil laboratory of Balai Geoteknik Jalan (Research Institute for Highways and Bridges), on clay soils, sands, and soil-concrete interface. Two materials were used for the experiments, i.e. sandy soils and clay soils. The surfaces are varied and also the shearing rates were determined 0.01 mm/minutes and 1.0 mm/minutes which is 100 times faster to obtain the damping effect of the soil and interface. Figure 2 shows the soil gradation of the sands, which is clean sand with medium to coarse particle size and mean grain size D50 = 0.8 mm.

Figure 2. Gradation of Sand Tested in Laboratory

The direct shear tests were conducted on soils and soil-concrete using normal stress of 18-72 kPa as shown on Table 1. The results of the test on sand are shown on Figure 3. It shows that higher shearing rate clearly shows the difference in results. The test results confirm that as the shearing rates substantially increased, there is an increase in the shear stress representing the effect of test rate.

Table 1. Variation of Normal Stress and Shearing Rate for Tests

Sample No.	Normal Stress, P (kg/cm ²)	Shearing Rate, V (mm/min)
I	0.18	0.01
		1.0
II	0.36	0.01
		1.0
III	0.72	0.01
		1.0

Figure 3. Results of Direct Shear Test on Sand with Different Shearing Rate and Normal Stresses

The test conducted on clay is by reconstituted sample from disturbed sample. The clay properties are shown on Table 2, and the soil grain size determined by hydrometer test is shown on Figure 4. The clay soil is high plasticity clay (CH) with 45.5% clay content, 45% of silts and 9.5% of sand. The clay sample was compacted to its maximum dry density under standard Proctor energy. The CBR values for compacted clay was 6.0% at 95% dry density and 7.52% at 100% density in soaked condition. The research was conducted to evaluate the shear strength of the soils as well as to generate damping characteristics.

Table 2. Properties of Clay for Tests

No.	Properties	Value
1	Liquid Limit (LL)	74
2	Plastic Limit (PL)	41
3	Plasticity Index (PI)	33
4	Shrinkage Limit	28
5	% Finer No. 200	90.52 %
6	Clay Fraction	45.5 %
7	Density	γ_{dmax} 1.21 gr/cm ³
		W_{opt} 41.80 %
8	CBR Standard (Soaked)	100% γ_d 7.52 %
		95% γ_d 6.00 %

Figure 4. Grain Size Distribution of Clay Soils for Test

To obtain shear stresses between soil and structural material, the direct shear test has been conducted on clay-mortar interface. The mortar is representative of pile concrete material. The tests conducted by varying the shearing rate, normal force, and roughness of the mortar. Schematic of test on clay-mortar interface is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Schematic of Test on Clay-Mortar Interface

Direct shear tests on clay conducted with shearing rate exactly follow the same rates as tests on sand. The results of tests are shown in Figure 6.

From the results shown in Figure 6, it gives the similar results as tests on sand. For the same value of normal force, the faster shearing rate, the bigger value of shear stress. The results also clearly show that the shear stress is directly proportional to the value of normal stress.

Figure 6. Results of Direct Shear Test on Clay with Different Shearing Rate and Normal Stresses

SURFACE ROUGHNESS

The roughness level of mortar is obtained by using British Pendulum Tester (BPT). Unit obtained from the test specified on British Pendulum Number (BPN). Shape and roughness of the mortar is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Roughness of mortar sample I and II (a), and Condition After Test on Clay-Mortar Interface (b)

Roughness level of mortar sample I and II, based on Indonesian Standard (SNI 4427: 2008) are 53 BPN and 72 BPN, respectively. Visually, the surface of mortar sample I is smoother than the surface of sample II. The clay-mortar sample have dimensions of 50 mm diameter and 12 mm thick, where both thickness of clay and mortar are 5.5 mm with 1.0 mm gap. The test results on clay-mortar interface is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Test Results on Clay-Mortar Interface with Different Shearing Rate and Mortar Gradation

From the test result, it shows that the rougher mortar surface, the bigger value of shear stress generated. Moreover, it is also shown the same result that the shear stress is directly proportional to the value of normal stress.

CALCULATION OF SMITH DAMPING PARAMETERS

Based on his experience, Smith (1960) proposed an equation:

$$\tau_t = \tau_s(1 + J_s v) \quad (1)$$

where:

- τ_t = Total Friction (kPa)
- τ_s = Instantaneous static friction (kPa)
- v = Pile velocity (m/s)
- J_s = Smith damping parameter (s/m)

Smith damping parameter, J_s can be back calculated since the parameter of τ_t , τ_s , and v are known or measured. Total friction, τ_t is specified as the shear stress of clay-mortar at shearing rate of 1.00 mm/min, while τ_s is specified as the shear stress of clay-mortar at shearing rate of 0.01 mm/min. In addition, pile velocity is also known and specified as the shear rate of 1.00 mm/min.

SMITH DAMPING ON SOILS

Figure 9 and Figure 10 show Smith damping calculated from direct shear test on soils. It is interesting that in sandy soils, the Smith damping is lower for high normal stress however, the clay soil yields higher Smith damping for higher normal stress. An important conclusion is that the Smith damping for soils are influenced by the value of normal stress.

Figure 9. Calculated Value of J_s from Direct Shear Test on Sand (c)

Figure 10. Calculated Value of J_s from Direct Shear Test on Clay (a)

SMITH DAMPING IN CLAY-CONCRETE INTERFACE

Test on soil-concrete interface were conducted on clay soils with $P = 0.80 \text{ kg/cm}^2$ and $P = 3.2 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. The trend is the Smith damping of soil-concrete interface is about half of the Smith damping for soils, and the value of the Smith damping is about 0.45 – 0.60 for clay.

Figure 11. Calculated Value of J_s from Direct Shear Test on Clay-Concrete Interface

From the results, the average values of J_s for clay-concrete, clay, and sand are 0.63 s/m, 1.2 s/m, and 1.5 s/m, respectively. The value obtained for soil-concrete interface is very similar as the recommended value of Smith damping from GRL (1993).

Table 3. Recommended Smith damping factors by GRL (1993)

	Non-Cohesive	Cohesive	Limestone
Skin	0.16	0.65	-
Toe	0.49	0.49	-

CONCLUSION

From this study, we can conclude that the different shearing rate will bring a significant result to shear-displacement curve. This is may be caused by the existence of damping, which appears when the soil subjected to fast shear/ displacement.

- The direct shear test with different shearing rate on soils and soil-concrete interface can be used to measure Smith damping of soils. This method is prospective to be developed.
- The Smith damping, J_s for soil-concrete interface is about half of those in soils. This is reasonable and the Smith damping for soil-concrete interface is similar to those recommended by GRL by GRL (1993).
- The speed of testing with 0.01 mm/min can be assumed to give τ_s and at a rate of 1.00 mm/min may be used to estimate Smith damping on soil-concrete interface. The actual speed in the field will be much higher.

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